

Timestamp	In what activity sector are you	DIRECT FATALITIES				SCHOOL DAYS LOST				HUMAN DEVELOPMENT				MENTAL HEALTH WELLBEING				CRITERIA RANKING Direct fa School (human + mental)	DIRECT FATALITIES				SCHOOL DAYS LOST				HUMAN DEVELOPMENT				MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL BEING				WEIGHTS										
		L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4		L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4	W1	W2	W3	W4			
2-18-2021 23:34:48	Education and research	5	6	7	9	9	6	8	6	9	7	8	6	9	8	7	5	9	8	7	5	0	0.25	0.5	1	0	1	0.667	0	0	0.333	0.667	0	0	1	0.5	0	0	0.75	0.5	0	0.5021	0.2343	0.1004	0.1632
2-18-2021 23:50:27	Education and research	2	3	3	3	10	2	10	1	10	5	5	1	9	9	5	1	9	8	9	8	0	1	1	1	0	1	1.111	1	0	1	0.444	0.444	0	1	1	0.5	0.3333	0.1667	0.3333	0.1667				
2-18-2021 23:53:16	Education and research	9	8	10	9	6	10	7	2	9	8	8	7	8	7	8	6	8	10	8	10	0.5	0	1	0.5	0.5	0	1	1	0	1	0.5	0.5	0	1	0	1	0.2000	0.3429	0.1453	0.3429				
2-18-2021 01:32:54	Education and research	8	5	9	6	8	6	9	6	8	6	8	4	8	7	6	4	6	4	6	7	0.75	0	1	0.25	0.667	0	1	0.25	0	1	0.5	0.5	0	1	0.75	0.5	0.2500	0.5000	0.2500	0.4000				
2-18-2021 23:56:46	Education and research	5	6	5	7	5	6	6	5	6	6	5	5	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	5	0	0.5	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.3429	0.3429	0.1143	0.2000								
2-19-2021 0:01:10	Education and research	6	5	6	7	5	7	5	6	6	6	5	5	5	6	5	5	5	6	5	5	0.5	0	0.5	1	0	1	0	0.5	1	1	0	0	0.2333	0.2333	0.1333	0.4000								
2-19-2021 0:02:05	Non-governmental sector	7	8	6	7	6	7	8	8	8	7	8	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	0.5	1	0	0.5	0	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.2000	0.2000	0.4000	0.2000								
2-19-2021 0:05:15	Education and research	5	6	7	8	9	7	5	1	5	6	6	8	5	5	7	9	10	9	9	9	0	0.333	0.667	1	1	0.75	0.5	0	0	0.333	0.333	1	0	0	0.5	1	0.4000	0.2000	0.2000	0.2000				
2-19-2021 0:06:05	Education and research	10	7	9	6	9	6	8	9	8	9	7	9	9	7	8	10	7	10	10	9	1	0.25	0.75	0	1	0	0.667	1	0.5	1	0	1	0.0870	0.3478	0.3478	0.2174								
2-19-2021 0:06:20	Healthcare / social care sys	9	8	10	9	6	10	7	2	9	8	9	10	7	7	8	6	8	10	8	10	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0.5	0.5	0.1667	0.3333	0.1667	0.3333								
2-19-2021 0:13:29	Government / Public admin	3	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4	3	4	4	3	4	3	3	3	3	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500				
2-19-2021 0:15:20	Education and research	8	7	9	6	3	4	6	10	4	5	4	7	5	5	8	5	4	6	8	8	0.667	0.333	1	0	0	0.143	0.429	1	0	0.333	0	1	0	0	1	0	0.0750	0.1750	0.3750	0.3750				
2-19-2021 0:21:04	Education and research	10	8	6	4	3	8	3	9	3	5	6	8	3	4	6	8	9	8	7	7	1	0.667	0.333	0	0	0.833	0	1	0	0.4	0.6	1	0.4444	0.2593	0.1481	0.1481								
2-19-2021 0:24:28	Education and research	5	4	8	10	5	4	9	5	9	6	5	2	10	9	6	4	7	10	8	5	0.167	0	0.667	1	0.2	0	1	0.2	1	0.571	0.429	0	0	1	0.833	0.333	0.1837	0.4898	0.2449	0.0816				
2-19-2021 0:39:13	Education and research	5	5	5	5	1	5	1	5	8	6	6	9	8	8	8	9	4	1	1	8	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0.667	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.2188	0.0781	0.0781	0.6250				
2-19-2021 0:55:14	Government / Public admin	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500								
2-19-2021 0:59:30	Private sector	4	3	2	1	1	3	2	4	1	2	3	4	2	1	3	4	10	10	10	10	0	0.667	0.333	0	0	0.667	0.333	1	0	0.333	0.667	1	0.333	0	0.867	1	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500				
2-19-2021 1:01:38	Education and research	4	5	7	9	3	7	5	2	9	6	4	2	9	7	4	2	9	4	3	4	0	0.2	0.6	1	0.2	1	0.6	0	1	0.571	0.286	0	0.6269	0.1418	0.0896	0.1418								
2-19-2021 1:33:16	Education and research	6	6	5	5	9	7	8	9	8	8	8	8	7	8	8	9	7	8	8	7	1	1	0	0	1	0	0.5	1	1	1	1	1	0.1667	0.3333	0.3333	0.1667								
2-19-2021 1:45:20	Education and research	1	6	7	10	1	1	10	1	1	1	10	1	1	1	10	1	10	8	9	9	0	0.556	0.667	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.4000	0.1333	0.2333	0.2333								
2-19-2021 2:13:27	Education and research	3	4	9	1	9	2	8	1	8	6	8	2	8	7	6	10	9	8	6	8	0.25	0.375	1	0	1	0.125	0.875	0	1	0.667	1	0	0.5	0.25	0	1	0.4000	0.2600	0.1000	0.2500				
2-19-2021 4:58:48	Education and research	10	8	7	6	8	6	5	7	6	8	9	6	6	7	8	5	9	7	7	7	1	0.5	0.25	0	1	0.333	0	0.667	0	0.667	1	0	0.5000	0.1667	0.1667	0.1667								
2-19-2021 5:13:59	Education and research	6	6	10	7	6	8	6	8	7	7	7	5	6	6	6	3	8	10	9	9	0	0	1	0.25	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0.1333	0.4000	0.2333	0.2333								
2-19-2021 5:33:53	Education and research	3	4	6	8	4	6	3	6	5	4	3	10	1	8	4	9	7	8	7	4	0	0.2	0.6	1	0.333	1	0	1	0	0.286	0.143	0	0.2600	0.4000	0.2600	0.0800								
2-19-2021 6:34:25	Education and research	2	5	10	2	2	3	9	2	2	2	6	1	1	4	10	1	4	7	8	8	0	0.375	1	0	0	0.143	1	0	0	0.333	1	0	0.0702	0.2201	0.3509	0.3509								
2-19-2021 6:41:34	Education and research	5	8	9	10	8	8	10	7	8	9	10	1	7	8	9	10	3	8	9	6	0	0.6	0.8	1	0.333	0.333	1	0	0.778	0.889	1	0	0.571	0.714	1	0	0.2174	0.3478	0.0870	0.3478				
2-19-2021 6:43:25	Education and research	7	8	9	4	10	8	10	6	10	7	7	4	10	7	5	1	8	6	5	4	0.6	0.8	1	0	1	0.5	1	0	1	0.5	0.5	0	0.5021	0.2343	0.1632	0.1004								
2-19-2021 7:47:52	Education and research	3	6	7	8	2	5	5	8	3	5	5	7	7	7	5	3	9	5	6	6	0	0.6	0.8	1	0	0.5	0.5	1	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.4598	0.0920	0.1494	0.2989								
2-19-2021 8:21:42	Education and research	7	5	4	2	9	7	5	2	9	5	5	1	8	8	5	2	9	7	6	6	1	0.6	0.4	0	1	0.714	0.429	0	1	0.5	0.5	0	0.5217	0.2174	0.1304	0.1304								
2-19-2021 8:27:10	Education and research	7	8	9	10	7	7	10	5	7	7	9	6	7	6	8	4	8	7	6	9	0	0.333	0.667	1	0.4	0.4	1	0	0.333	0.333	1	0	0.2727	0.1818	0.1091	0.4364								
2-19-2021 8:53:00	Government / Public admin	3	3	8	8	3	3	8	3	3	3	8	3	3	3	8	3	9	9	9	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500									
2-19-2021 8:57:03	Education and research	7	8	9	10	7	7	10	5	7	7	9	6	7	6	8	4	8	7	6	9	0	0.333	0.667	1	0.4	0.4	1	0	0.333	0.333	1	0	0.75	0.5	1	0	0.2727	0.1818	0.1091	0.4364				
2-19-2021 9:08:38	Education and research	7	9	4	10	6	8	4	10	5	9	4	6	4	2	9	4	9	7	5	8	0.5	0.833	0	1	0.333	0.667	0	1	0.2	1	0	0.4	0.286	0	1	0.286								
2-19-2021 9:45:12	Private sector	4	4	5	6	1	2	1	10	1	5	5	10	1	1	6	10	1	6	10	6	0	0	0.5	1	0	0.111	0	1	0	0.444	0.444	1	0	0	0.556	1	0.1429	0.2857	0.2857	0.2857				
2-19-2021 9:58:45	Education and research	9	8	8	7	1	5	1	8	5	9	9	4	3	3	7	8	5	9	8	8	1	0.5	0.5	0	0	0.571	0	1	0.2	1	1	0	0.0800	0.4000	0.2600	0.2600								
2-19-2021 10:07:08	Education and research	6	8	8	4	5	8	8	4	8	8	8	4	8	8	8	4	10	6	8	8	0.5	1	1	0	0.25	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0.4688	0.0938	0.2188	0.2188								
2-19-2021 10:19:53	Education and research	3	6	8	10	4	4	9	5	3	9	9	10	7	4	7	3	8	10	9	8	0	0.429	0.714	1	0	0.4	1	0.2	0	0.857	0.857	1	0.1481	0.4444	0.2593	0.1481								
2-19-2021 10:20:36	Government / Public admin	3	3	8	8	3	3	8	3	3	3	8	3	3	3	8	3	9	9	9	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500	0.2500									
2-19-2021 10:23:10	Education and research	5	6	6	5	4	8	3	6	5	5	7	5	5	6	6	7	9	7	7	7	0	1																						